

Awareness and Attitude towards Open Access in India's National Agricultural Research System

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ABSTRACT

Open Access movement is gathering momentum in NARS. While some of the institutes have established institutional repositories, there is no mandatory deposit of research outputs policy in NARS. In this paper, we present the results of a survey that was carried out to study attitude and awareness about open access among the NARS researchers in India using questions from American Society for Information Science and Technology's survey on 'Scholarly Publishing'. The results showed that nearly 50% of the researchers not aware of what is open access; however, when explained, 62% of them responded that they would deposit postprints in repositories but not preprints and datasets. Thirty two percent had strongly agreed that with open access, the quality would improve and 42% agreed that it would be easier to get hold of papers. This shows that with the increased open access advocacy and establishment repositories would solve the accessibility issues in NARS.

Keywords: Information science, Survey, Scientists, Agricultural Research, India

INTRODUCTION

Apropos to the Budapest Open Access Initiative (BOAI) in 2002, the seeds of movement of open access – unrestricted sharing and communication of scholarly literature via Internet were sown in India during the year 2004. Since then, various institutes/organizations have had established institutional repositories for depositing research outputs (scholarly literature). Till date in India, about 90 repositories have been established. However, this 'Open Access' movement's momentum is just gathering in the India's National Agricultural Research System (NARS). The NARS is the largest system of the world having establishments of agricultural universities & research institutes involving in education, research, and extension. In the NARS, till date established repositories related to agriculture field are viz., Eprints@IARI, Eprints@CMFRI, E-Repository@IIHR, DSpice@IISR, OpenAgri (Agropedia), RKMP, Krishi Prabha, ETD@UASD etc. When agriculture is a way of life in India and ~70% of its

people depend on agriculture, the access to agriculture information and data becomes crucial and at this background, a survey was carried out to understand what is the awareness and attitude of researchers in NARS towards 'Open Access' and for publicly sharing research outputs via open access repositories.

METHODOLOGY

The survey with title 'NARS Open Access Survey' was carried out during 2009-10 to find out the level of awareness of NARS researchers on open access and their attitude on sharing research outputs publicly. The survey had used the questions from the 'Scholarly Publishing Questionnaire' of the American Society for Information Science and Technology (ASIS&T) with their kind permission. The survey was set up using 'Lime Survey' a Free and Open-Source Software on Open Knowledge Society, Bangalore's web server space (now not in use) and was sent to a set of mailing list formed of randomly selected researchers in NARS from various sources. The survey link was posted on various research & social networking sites requesting the NARS researchers to participate. However, the survey received only 100 submissions with full responses from NARS researchers and results are as follows.

RESULTS

The profiles of the respondents showed that majority of the responders were male (91%), in which 85% are of <45 years age and have earned PhD (77%). As per the designation wise categorization, Assistant Professors (and equivalent) constituted 47% and Professors (and equivalent) 21%. Most of the respondents belonged to the disciplines viz., Animal Sciences, Genetics & Plant Breeding, Horticulture and Plant Physiology. It is interesting to note that almost of them are authors (98%) of various publications and 57% had also reviewed manuscripts and have had published at least five papers in the last three years (53%) (Fig. 1 and Table 1). Their top five favorite journals are Indian Journal of Agricultural Sciences (20%), Current Science (16%), Indian Journal of Horticulture (12%), Indian Journal of Genetics & Plant Breeding (11%) and Indian Journal of Animal Sciences (11%).

Fig.1. Profile of the NARS Respondents

Table 1. Number of Respondents and Number of Papers they Published

Number of Papers	Number of Respondents	
	In Last Three Years	In Their Career
0 – 10	75	35

11 – 20	7	26
21 – 30	3	17
31 – 40	0	7
41 – 50	0	5
> 50	0	6

When the respondents were asked about what their accessibility to the scholarly literature (Fig.2) is, It was found that 75% had difficulty to access the scholarly journal literature whereas, only 10% of the respondents expressed that they had excellent access to the literature. Forty six percent responded that it varies and sometimes they don't get the required literature and only 10% said that they have excellent access to the scholarly literature.

Fig.2. What is the accessibility of literature in NARS?

When they were asked where they do find or search for the scholarly literature (Fig.3), 82% have responded that they would search in Google scholar and about 80% search at the library subscribed print journals followed by online journals ~50%.

Fig.3. How NARS access scholarly literature?

Fig.4. How much NARS know about Open Access?

Eighty one percent of the respondents know that their research is funded by public funds. However, about 49% of them are not aware of what is 'Open Access'? (Fig. 4). And 66% had not published in any open access journals (Fig. 5). Whereas 30% of them responded that they know quite a lot of about 'Open Access'. When explained about what Institutional Repositories are, 62% had responded that they had not deposited their papers in any repositories but would like to deposit in future.

Fig. 5. Have NARS published a paper in an Open Access Journal?

After explaining what is 'Open Access' and asked what the characteristics of open access journals (OAJs) are they can attribute, 37% had agreed that OAJs are well indexed and 9% had strongly agreed to attribute them as radicals whereas, 8% as ephemerals. Thirty five percent had strongly agreed with the statement made on open access that authors would publish more, 33% had agreed that the quality would improve, 42% agreed that it would be easier to get hold of papers (Table 2).

Table. 2. NARS agreement or disagreement on statements about Open Access?

Statements about Open Access	Percentage of Respondents on Agreement to Disagreement on 5 to 1 scale				
	5	4	3	2	1
Archiving will suffer	9	12	32	23	24

Statements about Open Access	Percentage of Respondents on Agreement to Disagreement on 5 to 1 scale				
Authors will have less choice over where they publish	8	18	23	23	28
Authors will publish more	35	29	17	11	8
Few papers will be rejected	9	31	32	12	16
It will be easier to get hold of papers	42	29	18	8	3
Libraries will have more money to spend	32	24	23	11	10
Papers will become less concise	13	25	33	17	12
Print journals will gradually disappear	16	21	28	21	14
Publishers will improve their services to authors	29	37	22	8	4
Quality of papers will improve	33	30	22	12	3

When responders were asked what they find attractive among the various reasons while they consider for submitting a paper to a particular journal? About 61% have responded that speed of reviewing is very attractive (and important) followed by impact factor (47%), coverage by abstracting services (38%) and availability of the journal in an electronic version (37%) (Table 3).

Table. 3. What is attractive to NARS for submitting papers to journals?

Factor	Not at all attractive	Not attractive	Neutral	Attractive	Very attractive
Speed Review	7	6	6	20	61
Editorial Board	7	11	19	37	26
Rating	9	10	10	24	47
Popularity	3	8	7	45	37
Online	6	11	21	25	37
Hard copy	6	14	23	33	24
Easy	16	15	20	26	23
Abstracting	6	7	11	38	38
Scope	9	13	23	27	28

Sixty two percent of the responders replied that they have not deposited anything in Institutional Repositories but would like to deposit in future (Fig. 6). When they were asked what if they have personal or official website, what kinds of materials they would like to post on it. Fifty seven percent of them responded that they would post revised texts of papers that have been submitted for publication followed by technical reports (52%) (Fig. 7).

Fig. 6. Has NARS deposited any scholarly materials in a Repository?

Fig.7. What NARS would like to share on their personal/official websites?

The NARS researchers when posed with the question of what they do with the published research when it is freely available, more than 50% of the respondents agreed that they would use it freely in teaching and learning and 43% agreed that they would pass it on to interested party in electronic format. However, 34% of them disagreed with the statement of republishing it elsewhere in its entirety (Table 4.).

Table.4. NARS likeliness to use published research.

Likeliness to use published research	Percentage of Respondents on Agreement to Disagreement on 5 to 1 scale				
	5	4	3	2	1
Deal personally with any legal disputes when copyright is infringed	18	17	31	22	12
Pass it on in electronic form to a colleague or interested party	43	33	9	6	9
Personally deal with any permission request	23	25	34	11	7
Post it on an internal website	30	37	20	5	8
Post it on world wide web	34	26	25	8	7

Likeliness to use published research	Percentage of Respondents on Agreement to Disagreement on 5 to 1 scale				
Republish it elsewhere in its entirety	11	17	31	7	34
Use it freely in teaching and learning	53	30	10	3	4

The following points emerged in the survey about 'Open Access' and sharing of research outputs:-

- On personal websites they would like to post information about their work, expertise and list of publications etc.
- Many of them feel that datasets of projects are assets of scientists and institute and are the results of hard work and time. So, till they are published or IPR are secured, they should no be shared and posted. However, when they are published, they would like to share the data.
- On the open access journals, they expressed that one can know what is happening in their area of research and would help in sharing valuable scientific information/data among scientists which would help in better understanding of research.
- The open access journals are the need of hour and I strongly recommend them for many reasons viz., saving of paper, time and money, better peer reviewing and easier management of published work.
- Open access system will definitely change the concepts of publishing research articles and its accessibility on a much broader scale.

The following comments were made by the respondents of the survey.

- Open access journal brings freedom to researchers and one can know what is happening in their area of research.
- Open access journals would help in sharing valuable scientific information/data among scientists which would help in better understanding of research.
- Open access system will definitely change the concepts of publishing research articles and its accessibility on a much broader scale
- The awareness about open access journals among NARS scientists is quite poor.
- The open access journals are the need of hour and I strongly recommend them for many reasons viz., saving of paper, time and money, better peer reviewing and easier management of published work.

DISCUSSION

The survey revealed that about 75% of the researchers are not able to access the scholarly literature what they want. This is inspite of good efforts being made in NARS by making available the scholarly published journals online via CeRA (Consortium of e-Resources in Agriculture) project. Most of the responders of survey are the authors and they are looking at the popularity of the journal and its speed of reviewing for submitting their papers. It is revealed that about 62% of them have not deposited their outputs in Institutional Repositories. This is mainly because of non availability of the repositories for their institution or their discipline. The Agropedia which is a multi-disciplinary repository is just being populated by the partners and few others. When the respondents were made aware of what is Institutional Repository, most of them had responded that they have not deposited but would be depositing in future. When asked, what they would deposit and what they would not, many

responded that they would deposit the revised texts of the manuscripts but not any data sets. In the comments they had mentioned that they fear for the IPR theft and they would not share any unpublished datasets. However, they would do when the data is published. More than 90% of the respondents are aware of what is Open Access but 66% have not published in any Open Access Journal. In NARS, very few open access journals are available and now with the transformation of the two flagship journals of ICAR into open access, the momentum is gaining and the authors are looking forward to publish in open access journals. The survey analysis shows some similarities with the latest CIARD survey on 'Researcher Attitudes and Behavior towards the openness' in Agriculture and Related Fields (Edge et al., 2012). The India's NARS researchers are in accordance with the other agricultural researches around the world in the attitude towards 'openness'. As per the CIARD survey, the researchers feel that freely and openly available outputs could be in the hands of the individual and some would act for making open their outputs. However, many lack the required resources and institutional policies to drive 'Openness'.

CONCLUSIONS

The responders of survey had given a mixed response for majority of the questions. Majority of the NARS researchers have less access to the scholarly research and 66% had not published in open access journals. However, most of them favoured it when they were explained about open access and 62% responders stated that they would deposit their papers in institutional repositories. As per the call given by Budapest Open Access Initiative it is the scholarly societies which should come formed for the launch of open access journals and the institutes in NARS should establish open access repositories and adopt open access policy for their research outputs. For this, a strong open access advocacy and capacity building should be there in NAS which would definitely enable the researchers in NARS to showcase and share their research for public good.

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